

ЎЗМУ ХАБАРЛАРИ

ВЕСТНИК НУУз

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МИРЗО УЛУҒБЕК НОМИДАГИ ЎЗБЕКИСТОН МИЛЛИЙ
УНИВЕРСИТЕТИ ИЛМИЙ ЖУРНАЛИ

**ЖУРНАЛ
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**2022
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ТОШКЕНТ – 2022

Санчик Д. Учет биологических особенностей бегунов на короткие дистанции при индивидуализации тренировочного процесса	158
Сойинов Ж. Физикага ихтисослашган мактаб ўқувчиларида баҳолашга оид масалалар ёрдамида тадқиқотчилик кўникмаларини шакллантириш	161
Suvonova O. Mexanika bo'limi mavzularini o'qitishda pedagogik dasturiy vositalardan foydalanish usullari	164
Усманов М. Мифологизациянинг кундалик онгда намоён бўлиши	168
Файзуллаева З. Ўрта Осиё халқлари миллий кадрятларининг таълим-тарбия жараёнидаги ўрни	172
Fozilova M. The importance of using interactive methods in teaching english to students of architectural universities	176
Xalimova M. Tadbirkorlik psixologiyasini rivojlantirishining zamonaviy tendentsiyalari	180
Шопулатов А. Мамлакатимизда жисмоний тарбия ва спорт муассасалари фаолиятини илмий-методик таъминлаш ишларини такомиллаштириш	183
Yusufaliyeva A. Oilaviy munosabatlarda bolalarning o'z-o'zini anglashi	187
Якубов С. Ички ишлар тизими ходимларида шахслараро муносабатлар шаклланишининг психологик асослари	192

Филология

Abjalova M. Sinkretizm – lingvistik hodisa sifatida	195
Абдувахобова М. Оғзаки ва ёзма фольклор дискурси тафовутида дейктик воситаларнинг мақоми	199
Amanbayeva D. A sense of duty as a specific linguistic concept	202
Амирова З. Концептнинг лингвокультурологиядаги базавий категорияларидан бири сифатида	207
Axmedova M. Mumtoz adabiyotlarda “ma’naviyat” tushunchasining talqini	211
Bahridinova M. Bolalarga nemis tilini o'rgatishda ayrim muhim tavsiyalar	214
Dadaboyeva G. Stylistic function of medical terminologies in literary works	218
Ёдгоров Ш. Куръони Каримда учрайдиган эмбриология соҳасига оид терминларнинг семантик таҳлили (Канадалик эмбриолог Кейс Леон Муурнинг тадқиқот ишлари асосида)	221
Jo'rayeva B., Tosheva D., Ubaydova H. O'zbek xalq maqollarida kontekstual antonimlar	225
Икрамова А. Шеъринг драмада синкретиклик хусусиятининг намоён бўлиши	229
Islomov J. Erkin A'zamning “Tanho qayiq” dramasida xarakterlar tahlili	232
Йигиталиева З. Тил модал структурасининг замонавий талқини	234
Ким О., Мухитдинова Н. Выбор героя и особенности конфликта в социально-психологической драме 1930-х годов	238
Mirсанов В. Nemis tilida intralingvistik omillar asosida voqelangan ikkilamchi nomlashlar	242
Муқимова Г. Халқ оғзаки ижодида олманинг кўчма маънолари лингвопоэтикаси	245
Мустофақулова М. Инглиз тилидан ўзбек тилига таржимада “sly” яъни “айёр, маккор” сифатининг коннотатив маъносидаги ижобий, нейтрал ва салбий маъноларда ифодаланиши	248
Nizomova M. Ingliz va o'zbek tillarida integratsiya sharoitida pedagogik terminologiya, ta'limdagi jarayonlar va pedagogika fanida atamalarni rivojlantirishning yetakchi tendentsiyalari	251
Nurova Y. O'zbek xalq paremlarining lingvistik tadqiqi	255
Орипов Д. Ўғузхон: жаҳонгирми ёхуд эпик қаҳрамон?!	258
Раджабова Х. Хавфсиз туризмни таъминлаш бўлинмалари фаолиятида фойдаланиладиган юридик ва туризмга оид атамаларнинг тизимли таҳлили	262
Ruzieva M. Biological feature of the human linguistic system	267
Садикова Д. Муслихабегим Мискин соқийномаларининг ўзига хос хусусиятлари	270
Sanakulov J. Globallashuv jarayonida multimadaniyat va til munosabatlari	273
Turgunova R. Methodological basis of writing as a complex process	276
Urishev A. Developing pair-work interaction in CLT classes	279
Усманова М. Алишер Навоий асарлари тилида маданий экин номларининг семантик-услубий хусусиятлари	282
Xakimova N. 5-sinf o'quvchilarida o'qib tushinish ko'nikmasini aniqlashning tajribaviy tadqiqi	285
Хасанов А. Инсонга хос хусусиятлар, ҳаракатлар ва ижтимоий муносабатларни ифодаловчи сўзларнинг адабий тилни бойитиш имкониятлари	289
Шомирзаев М. Мактаб ўқувчиларини халқ хунармандчилигига ўргатишда инновацион таълим методларидан фойдаланиш	293
Эгамбердиев Ф. О лингвистических характеристиках имен прилагательных и слов категории состояния в английском и узбекском языках	297
Eshquvvatov U. Bo'lajak muhandislarni o'qitishda axborot-kommunikatsion texnologiyalarning o'rni	301

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BIOLOGICAL FEATURE OF THE HUMAN LINGUISTIC SYSTEM

Annotation

The paper discusses evolution of a language and its biological factors that occur in its emergence. Indeed, the problem of the origin of natural human language is not purely linguistic. It is solved within the framework of the complex problem "The origin of man, society, consciousness, language". The data available to modern science is sufficient only to put forward general hypotheses. The biological hypotheses of the origin of language include the theory of onomatopoeia and the theory of interjections. According to the theory of onomatopoeia, language arose as a result of the fact that a person imitated the sound (and non-sound) features of named objects.

Key words: Language, biological factors, linguistic system, evolution, hypotheses, scientific theories, nature

БИОЛОГИЧЕСКАЯ ОСОБЕННОСТЬ ЯЗЫКОВОЙ СИСТЕМЫ ЧЕЛОВЕКА

Аннотация

В статье рассматривается эволюция языка и его биологические факторы, которые имеют место при его возникновении. Действительно, проблема происхождения естественного человеческого языка не является чисто лингвистической. Она решается в рамках комплексной проблемы «Происхождение человека, общества, сознания, языка». Имеющихся у современной науки данных достаточно лишь для выдвижения общих гипотез. К биологическим гипотезам происхождения языка относятся теория звукоподражания и теория междометий. Согласно теории звукоподражания, язык возник в результате того, что человек подражал звуковым (и незвуковым) признакам названных предметов.

Ключевые слова: Язык, биологические факторы, языковая система, эволюция, гипотезы, научные теории, природа

INSON LISONIY TIZIMINING BIOLOGIK XUSUSIYATI

Annotatsiya

Maqolada til evolyutsiyasi va uning rivojida kechuvchi biologik omillar to'g'risida fikr yuritiladi. Darhaqiqat, tabiiy inson tilining kelib chiqishi muammosi sof lingvistik emas va u "Inson, jamiyat, ong, tilning kelib chiqishi" murakkab muammo doirasida hal etiladi. Zamonaviy ilm-fanda mavjud bo'lgan ma'lumotlar faqat umumiy farazlarni ilgari surish uchun yetarlidir. Tilning kelib chiqishi haqidagi biologik gipotezalarga onomatopeya nazariyasi va interjeksion nazariyasi kiradi. Onomatopeya nazariyasiga ko'ra, til odamning muayyan nomga ega bo'lgan obyektlarning tovush (va tovushsiz) xususiyatlariga taqlid qilishi natijasida paydo bo'lgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Til, biologik omillar, til tizimi, evolyutsiya, farazlar, ilmiy nazariyalar, tabiat.

Introduction. The origin of language is an integral part of the problem of the origin of man and human society. People have long been interested in questions related to language. Why are only people, unlike all other species of living beings living on Earth, able to communicate through language? How did the language come about?

Even before the advent of scientific theories and hypotheses, a person sought to comprehend the questions of the origin of the language with the help of legends. The legendary ideas of the ancients about the origin of the language, although fictional in their basis, nevertheless allow us to get closer to some of the origins of widely known theories. Let's look at a few legends.

Literature Review. According to the Papuan legend, the creator demes lit a fire from still raw bamboo - the material from which people themselves were formed. The bamboo cracked from the heat, splinters stretched in different directions, which is why the first people had arms and legs, and eyes, ears, nostrils on their heads. And suddenly there was a loud crack: "Wa-a-ah!" - it was the first people who opened their mouths, and they found the gift of speech [1].

Often in such legends, the central figure is a sage who teaches people the language. It was such a gray-haired old man who, according to Estonian legend, gathered the leaders of the tribes scattered over the earth who could not speak. The

elder lit a fire and put a cauldron of water on it [2]. People who came listened to the sounds of boiling water and learned to pronounce them. Therefore, in some languages there are many hissing sounds, in others - whistling. The sage taught the Estonians the language he spoke himself. That is why the Estonian language is supposedly the most euphonious.

According to the Bible, "in the beginning was the word", that is, the language existed before man, was inherent in God and was given to man by God. But how then to explain why people speak different languages? This explains the biblical myth of the Tower of Babel. According to this legend, after the Flood, humanity was represented by one people who spoke the same language. From the east, people came to the land of Shinar (in the lower reaches of the Tigris and Euphrates), where they decided to build a city (Babylon) and a tower as high as heaven in order to "make a name for themselves" [3]. God, seeing the city and the tower, reasoned: "Now nothing will be impossible for them". And he put an end to the daring deed: he mixed the languages that the builders would no longer understand each other, and scattered people around the world. As we know, ancient man needed myths to explain the world, to interpret what was incomprehensible in it. With the development of science, man began to try to explain the origin of the language not with myths, but with theories and hypotheses.

It is evident from the abovementioned myths that the problem of the origin of natural human language is not purely linguistic. Its solution can only be achieved through the joint efforts of representatives of history, archeology, geology, anthropology, biology, psychology and many other sciences. The question of the origin of language has been of interest to mankind since ancient times. The idea of people getting a language from some higher powers was embodied in the creation theory (lat. *creo* - I create, I create) [4]. The first answer to the question of the origin of the language gives religion, the church: it is the Almighty who created man and everything that exists on earth. God apparently also created language. This hypothesis is called the theological (divine) theory of the origin of language.

Research methodology. In ancient linguistics, the question of the origin of language was raised within the framework of general philosophical discussions about the essence of language. In Greek science, there were two theories of language and its origin [5]:

- biological conditionality of the emergence of language;

- artificiality, the conscious nature of the emergence of language in society. These two competing trends continued to exist in European linguistics of the Middle Ages and the Renaissance, and then the New Age. Among the conditions for the emergence of language, factors associated with the development of the human body, and factors associated with the transformation of the primitive herd into society, were distinguished. Therefore, many hypotheses of the origin of the language can be divided into two main groups - biological theories and social theories [6].

Biological theories explain the origin of language by the evolution of the human body - the sense organs, the speech apparatus, the brain. They consider the emergence of language as the result of a long development of nature. Of the biological theories, the most famous are onomatopoeic and interjection. The onomatopoeic theory explains the origin of language by the evolution of hearing organs that perceive the cries of animals. Language arose, according to this theory, as a result of imitation by animals or as an expression of an impression about a named object. The onomatopoeic theory is based on two assumptions [7]: 1) the first words were onomatopoeia; 2) the sound in the word is symbolic, the meaning reflects the nature of things. However, there are few onomatopoeic words in the language and they are different in different languages. The basis for such views was that in all languages there really are onomatopoeic words, such as woof-woof, cuckoo, meow, shadow, ding, bam. But, firstly, there are relatively few such words. Secondly, the words most needed by people and the most commonly used do not reveal even a hint of imitating any sounds: water, earth, sky, sun, grass, man, smart, walk, think, etc. Thirdly, in order to imitate the sounds of nature surrounding a person with combinations of sounds, one must have a very flexible speech, which implies its long previous development. It is hardly possible in our time to take seriously the hypothesis of onomatopoeia; it is jokingly called the "woof-woof" theory.

Interjection (or reflex) theory explains the origin of language by the experiences that a person experiences. The first words are involuntary cries, interjections, provoked by the sensory perception of the world. In the course of further development, cries acquired a symbolic meaning. In the onomatopoeic theory, the external world was the stimulus for the appearance of words, and in the interjection theory, the inner world of people, their emotions. The first words, according to this theory, are involuntary cries, interjections, reflexes. They emotionally expressed pain or joy, fear or despair, hunger or pleasure. The impetus for the appearance of words, therefore, was the inner world of man. Some

supporters of the hypothesis under consideration admitted that interjection words arose only in the distant past, and later they developed according to the laws of word formation and independently of involuntary emotional cries.

Analysis and results. One cannot, of course, deny the participation of emotions and will in the development of language. But it is impossible to agree with the hypothesis of the interjectional origin of words, because she sees the main reason for their occurrence in the individual mental states of a person. The contradictions inherent in the explanation of the origin of the language from interjections served as the appearance of the comic name of this theory - "pah-pah" theory [8]. After all, no child will speak until he is surrounded by talking people, no matter how strong emotions he may experience. This is irrefutable evidence in favor of the opinion about the social conditioning of the birth of human speech.

Onomatopoeic and interjection theories focus on the study of the origin of the mechanism of speaking, mainly in psychophysiological terms. In these theories, the biological side of the issue is exaggerated, the origin of the language is considered exclusively in terms of the origin of speech, without connection with the development of human society.

Social theories explain the emergence of language by social needs that arose in labor and as a result of the development of human consciousness.

At the end of the 70s, 19th century the German philosopher L. Noiret put forward a working theory of the origin of language, or the theory of labor cries, according to which language arose in the process of joint labor activity of primitive people as one of the means of organizing and coordinating this activity [9]. The theory of labor cries is considered by some as a variant of the interjection theory.

All scientists emphasized the special role in the formation of human consciousness and sound speech of the "kinetic language" - the language of gestures and pantomime. The German philosopher and psychologist W. Wundt is considered the founder of the theory of the origin of language from gestures. Wundt believed that originally there were two languages - the language of sounds and the language of gestures. Gradually, the sound language improves, and the sign language begins to play a supporting role.

Man is a biosocial being whose nature combines biological and social qualities. Therefore, the development of the language was influenced by both social and biological factors.

Biological factors include:

- upright posture, as a result of which the position of the brain relative to the ground changed, the volume of the brain gradually increased, hands were freed;

- development of the hand, especially fine motor skills, which, as you know, stimulate the development of speech;

- the presence of sound signals in monkeys - human ancestors. These signals served as the physiological basis for the sound speech of a person of the modern type;

- development of the larynx, the physiological ability to articulate speech. In the process of historical development, some organs of the human body acquired secondary functions, forming together the speech apparatus: lips, teeth, lungs, nose, tongue, larynx.

A. Schleicher was the founder of the naturalistic (or biological) direction in linguistics. He outlined his views on language in the works: "The Language of Europe in a Systematic Illumination" (1850), "On the Morphology of Language" (1859), "Darwin's Theory and the Science of Language" (1863, Russian translation 1864), "The Meaning of Language for the natural history of mankind" (1865, Russian translation 1868), etc. He believed that language should be considered as a creation of nature, because a person is

powerless to change anything in the language at will, just as he cannot change the structure of his body.

Besides, he wrote: "All the languages that we have been tracing for a long time give grounds for the conclusion that they are in constant and continuous change. Languages, these natural organisms formed from sound matter, moreover, the highest of all show their properties natural organism, not only in the fact that they are all classified into genera, species, subspecies, etc., but also in the fact that their growth occurs according to certain laws [10].

After the publication of Ch. Darwin's work "The Origin of Species and Natural Selection" (1859), A. Schleicher affirms the understanding of language as a living organism, and not metaphorically, but literally. On this basis, he transfers the idea of the life of a living organism to the life of a language: as a separate animal or plant, a language is born, reaches maturity, gives offspring and dies.

Conclusion recommendations. The significance of the scientific ideas and works of A. Schleicher is great: he contributed to the development in historical linguistics of the principle of consistency and the method of reconstructing the parent language; morphological and genealogical classifications have firmly entered the general theory of language; consideration of the creation of language as the humanization of nature has become a component of the doctrine of the origin of language and thinking. However, such provisions of the theory of naturalism as explaining the reasons for the evolution of language only by biological factors, characterizing the Indo-European languages as the most modern, separating the development and history of the language from the functioning and history of society, have been criticized since the moment they were put forward.

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